

THE MAIN ASPECTS OF SALES CONTRACTS IN THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract. This article Uzbekistan republic of monetary policy in the conditions of buying, selling contracts, maintaining for necessary which is economic knowledge and conclusions quotes.

Key words: monetary, banking, money, finance, resources, market

To enter. Uzbekistan's monetary policy was last twenty years in economic growth, an important factor is, of the republic of resources, the capacity of effective and flexible management capabilities, opening gave. Uzbekistan's monetary policy, its own specific features in the country done is being of the reforms , the significance and the target direction with associated is, of them the essence market economic system, the gradual creation is. In the republic of radical economic reforms of the economy to market relations in conditions of performance, providing almost all credit-bank structure is a new one to create your require will.

The main part.

The Uzbekistan economy created macroeconomic conditions of the essence of the following consists of:

- enterprises state production and customization of work ownership form of whether regardless of all the ambassador receives' compliance of businesses for primary terms to the formation of the opportunity it gave;
- secondary valuable securities market primary and dynamic development from the appearance to be, as well as, a number of tax benefits that present be, too local, too foreign potential investors for favorable investment environment to create that provides;

- his money and payment area, two - level banking system institutionalization to macroeconomic stabilizing the policy implementation is increasing for all necessary conditions are created, this here is the central bank monetary policy in the leading role is played;
- The legislative framework for the development of commercial banks activities resources attract to and them the credit give and investment - making for the use of policy out heading is that for commercial purposes , who aspired for independent financial organizations of the status of strengthening;
- the ambassador receives running the market to form o' the tooth in the context of the commercial bank, the organization of as a result of small business manufacturing and banking field, in particular the former state banks with the competition of the basis of development;
- financial activities feature specialized commercial banks of Uzbekistan republic of the foreign economic activity national bank, "Asaka" state joint-stock commercial bank", "Uzpromstroybank" joint-stock commercial industrial construction bank and others as appear to get come.
- major and o'the central bank of the economy Real sector enterprises with relations to be deepening their economic stabilize and development.

Commercial banks activities permanent basis in central bank by controlled is and regulated shall be, this banking system stability, support , and deposit and creditors' interests to protect will. Central bank commercial bank lending activities, the effects of the process of their resources and such fit on the basis of credit options, the size of the increase or reduction of providing measures of their own into gets. Practice that shows, the central bank for this purpose for the following main mechanisms: uses: open market operations; commercial banks and the central bank at the rate of re-financing; mandatory reserve requirements.

Republic finance-banking system reform to further enhancement and stability to increase, the banks and the entire finance banking system, the activity of

evaluation of the approaches and of the system is a radical change, universal of international norms, standards and assessment according to the bank of the activities of the organization of a high level of out of that one in order:

1. Republic finance-banking system further reform to and the stability of increasing the main either of as the following are identified:

❖ the bank further, this sector to private capital, attract to, resource base to increase, assets quality, improve, the bank is the work of improving at the expense of the federal constitution to the committee by the set international standards and requirements in accordance with the bank's financial and liquidity increase;

❖ deposit for guarantees strengthen and population and foreign investors confidence in the further strengthening on systemic action see deposits and deposit new attractive types introduction to, bank service products, the range expand either with the bank system, the population and the ambassador receives subjects to city funds the world bank turnover wide attract to;

❖ leading international companies by methodology international norms, criteria and standards - based commercial banks, and in general financial-banking system, the activity of evaluation and analysis of the modern system of the introduction to and individual banks and the entire banking system of the whole world take I did high level output either development objective is to evaluate the opportunity to gives valuation the level;

❖ finance-bank activity of the normative and legal base improvement, in accordance with the time requirements and the adoption of existing and new international norms and standards and methodology add Legislative and normative documents;

❖ to increase the investment activity of commercial banks, commercial banks involved in the financing of investment projects of the further expansion of the city, from the examination of projects check-in passengers and risk assessment system loans on the emergence of problematic debt to the way methodology the as on

measures browsing through commercial bank loan portfolio of the constant go counted for and the quality to improve;

❖ in addition to the bank from financial institutions, credit unions, leasing, and audit firms to enhance the role and development of the network of international norms and standards in accordance with their among efficiency and effectiveness to ensure, they are services range expand, financial market infrastructure, the strengthening of institutions;

❖ funding the development of small business and private entrepreneurship, employment and improving the wellbeing of the population as the most important tool of micro-financing the sphere of the development;

❖ new approaches in the formation of commercial banks and the introduction of modern technologies and methods of accounting and reporting of technical, financial and banking information and improve the quality level of its leading international rating agencies of the requirements in accordance with the wide;

❖ in the world of commercial banks and financial institutions of the republic accepted standards, are the methodology and valuation of the system to work, able, prepared in a professional manner with the consolidation of highly qualified professionals in financial and banking activities in the field of further improvement of the system of training and retraining.

2. In the years 2011-2015 and the financial and banking system of the republic of priority directions of increasing the stability indicator to achieve high ratings and further reform international has developed a program, including:

✓ Further reform of the banking system of the republic in 2011-2015, and to increase the stability indicator to achieve high ratings on complex and international measures;

✓ The 2011-2015 years of the republic, micro-financing sector and banks in addition to financial sector further development measures.

3. 2011-2012 year, the bank supervision on the federal constitution to the committee of the new recommendations gradual introduction to, as well as, from the bank in addition to credit organizations activities over control of the improvement on the decision accepted was.

- ✓ commercial banks capital adequacy on the demands increase;
- ✓ commercial banks capital structure in their crisis events, the impact resistance providing to stabilize reserves creation;
- ✓ bank of the credit organizations for additional mandatory economic standards introduction was.

4. Commercial bank given bankrupt enterprises of property on the basis of the organization of the ambassador receives compliance entities:

- Uzbekistan Republic President, 2008-19 years-in November of orders 2-in handle by implied tax benefits of a strategic investor had sold after three years within to use the right has;
- 2011-from 1 January of the year starting in the republic of work and of ministers, ministries and by approved list of citizens work production modernization to and expansion for out who came raw, materials and but the official delegations for servicing a part of for customs of lov(customs clearance of that except to from the pros in 2 years, a period of released are.

Conclusion. In so doing, the world economy, monetary and financial institutions work in a large experience has if, their economy, the overall money with regulated in, market liquidity to maintain, payments for the effective implementation of the increase, fund investments held as the complexity of the role of evaluate to allows. This that shows, the country has a market economy transition in the context of financial and economic stabilizing both a number of problems to solve to on foreign experience with you to get acquainted certain interest evoke.

Also, Uzbekistan monetary policy of the last twenty years in economic growth, an important factor is, of the republic of resources, the capacity of effective

and flexible management capabilities, opening gave. Including scientifically analyzed the development of small business and business, and the legal basis, at this time financially support small business and business, the latter is amended and the rules for this branch of national legislation are added. The widespread introduction of new pedagogical technologies in teaching students of higher educational institutions and the effective use of innovative technologies are the main support for improving the quality of education.

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